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Assessing extended sequence signals flanking the transcription factor binding sites

Kateřina Balážová Faltejsková^{1,2}, Jiří Vondrášek^{2,3}.

¹ Computer Science Institute, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

² Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

³ Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

Transcription factor (TF) binding is primarily driven by short DNA motifs (~5–20 base pairs), yet the role of the surrounding sequence context is less clear. Biophysical studies (e. g. molecular dynamics simulations) suggested that flanking DNA influences TF binding only within a limited range of ~10–20 bp beyond the core motif. However, such short-range effects cannot explain why state-of-the-art deep learning models like Enformer or Basenji achieve better in vivo TF occupancy predictions when given much larger DNA sequence windows (hundreds to thousands of base pairs).

To address this discrepancy, we conducted a large-scale analysis of **53 ChIP-seq datasets** covering diverse TFs and cell lines, and we validated key observations with targeted **Cut&Tag** experiments. By aligning TF binding peak sequences and examining various sequence features, we quantified how these features change across the regions flanking each binding site.

We observed significant shifts in **base composition** (GC% and dinucleotide frequencies), **predicted DNA shape features** (e.g. minor groove width), and even the primary TF's **motif affinity** over long distances (several hundred to **thousands** of base pairs) upstream and downstream of the peak center. These trends persist far beyond the immediate ~20 bp neighborhood of the motif.

In short, the **span of the affected sequence** (hundreds to thousands of bp) was **consistently large** for different TFs and cell lines. The specific features that change (e.g. GC content vs. particular shape parameters) vary by TF and cell line, but almost every case shows a long-range context effect rather than a purely local one. These findings reveal that TF binding sites reside within expansive sequence context domains that were previously underappreciated.

Improved validation and refinement of biomolecular structures

Sahra Setenay Baran¹, Paulína Božíková¹, Jiří Černý¹

¹ Laboratory of Structural Bioinformatics of Proteins, Institute of Biotechnology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, BIOCEV, Vestec, Czechia

We present a further development of datasets and methods available in our laboratory for improved validation and refinement of biomolecular structures. We are building on synergies of data and tools involving structural alphabets [1-3] and flexibility of biomolecules [4,5].

The conformation- and location-dependent flexibility and solvation behavior derived from high quality non-redundant biomolecular structural data was employed for improvement of protocols for validation and refinement of biomolecular structures.

We extracted normalized B factor values of protein residues derived from high resolution structural data and collected distributions for protein residues in the interior and residues at the surface, either not found in contacts or involved in direct or water mediated contacts with biomolecular binding partners.

For structure validation we compared how well the B factor distribution in a model follows the corresponding reference distribution. The expected reference distribution from high-resolution structures can be also used prior to structure refinement replacing the currently used uniform B factor values. This can improve the convergence as well as accuracy of the structure refinement.

Keyword: B-factor, Protein, Re-refinement, SASA

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Does the specific *CENH3* variant direct the B chromosome to its own elimination?

Bojdová T^{1,2}, Hloušková L^{1,2}, Holušová K¹, Svačina R¹, Hřibová E¹, Ilíková I¹, Thiel J³, Kim G³, Pleskot R⁴, Houben A³, Bartoš J^{1*} and Karafiátová M^{1*}

¹ Institute of Experimental Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Centre of Plant Structural and Functional Genomics, Šlechtitelů 31, 779 00 Olomouc, Czech Republic

² Department of Cell Biology and Genetics, Faculty of Science, Palacky University, Šlechtitelů 27, 779 00 Olomouc, Czech Republic

³ Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK), 06466 Seeland OT Gatersleben, Germany

⁴ Institute of Experimental Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Laboratory of Integrative Structural Biology, Rozvojová 263, 165 00 Praha 6 - Lysolaje, Czech Republic

*Correspondence: bartos@ueb.cas.cz; karafiatova@ueb.cas.cz

B chromosomes are extra, dispensable chromosomes found in many species. Unlike standard chromosomes, B chromosomes do not follow typical inheritance patterns and can exhibit unique behaviors, including selective elimination. The elimination of specific DNA sequences, including complete chromosome loss, is a crucial evolutionary process that has been observed in diverse organisms. However, the molecular basis of chromosome-specific elimination remains poorly understood. Our research investigates the tissue-specific elimination of *Sorghum purpureosericeum* B chromosomes during embryo development, aiming to identify key molecular players involved in this process.

We have generated the first reference genome for *S. purpureosericeum*, providing a valuable resource for studying B chromosome biology. Then, using *in situ* visualization, transcriptomic profiling, and gene-enrichment analysis, we identified 28 candidate genes potentially involved in B chromosome elimination. These genes encode B-specific variants of proteins associated with mitotic processes, suggesting a link between chromosomal behavior and protein function. A particularly intriguing candidate is the B-specific variant of centromeric histone 3 (CENH3). *In silico* protein modeling revealed that the B-specific amino acid substitutions in CENH3 localize to domains interacting with the inner kinetochore protein CENP-C. The presence of similar B chromosome specific CENH3 variants in other plant species exhibiting chromosome elimination further supports this finding.

Our results suggest that the B chromosome of *S. purpureosericeum* is identified within the karyotype through its unique CENH3 variant, potentially marking it for elimination. This recognition mechanism may extend beyond the elimination of the B chromosome in *S. purpureosericeum*, potentially playing a role in other processes that selectively target specific chromosomes.

PDBCharges: Quantum-mechanical partial atomic charges for PDB structures

Ondřej Schindler^{1,2}, Gabriela Bučeková^{1,2}, Tomáš Svoboda^{1,2,3}, Adrián Rošinec^{1,2,3}, Tomáš Raček^{1,2}, Dominik Tichý², Karel Berka⁴, Radka Svobodová^{1,2}

¹ CEITEC – Central European Institute of Technology, Masaryk University, 625 00, Brno, Czech Republic,

² National Centre for Biomolecular Research, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, 625 00, Brno, Czech Republic,

³ Institute of Computer Science, Masaryk University, 602 00, Brno, Czech Republic,

⁴ Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, 779 00, Olomouc, Czech Republic

The PDB is the largest database of experimentally determined protein structures, containing more than 230 thousands of structures. A clue to the chemical reactivity of proteins is the electron density distribution, which is usually approximated by partial atomic charges. Due to the size and high variability of the structures stored in the PDB database, there is not yet a universal and accurate tool for calculating the partial atomic charges of these structures. For this reason we introduce the web application PDBCharges: a tool for the quick calculation of partial atomic charges for protein structures from PDB. The charges are calculated by the recent semiempirical quantum mechanical method GFN1-xTB reproducing PBE0/TZVP/CM5 charges. The computed partial atomic charges can be downloaded in common data formats or visualised via the powerful Mol* viewer. The PDBCharges application is freely available at <https://pdbcharges.biodata.ceitec.cz/> with no login requirement.

Explainable AI for Pharmacophore-Based Drug Activity Prediction

Joanna Ceklarz¹, Krystyna Waniová², Wim Dehaen¹, Tomasz Danel³, Martin Šícho¹

¹ CZ-OPENSOURCE: National Infrastructure for Chemical Biology, Department of Informatics and Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

² Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland

³ Faculty of Chemistry, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland

The integration of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) into drug discovery has, by leveraging advanced molecular representations, opened new avenues for predicting drug activity. Pharmacophore representations are commonly used by medicinal chemists to identify and visualize structures necessary for biological function [1]. Using them as representations of molecules for GNN training has yet untapped potential in deep learning. In addition, deep learning architectures, to which GNNs belong, despite their unparalleled performance in many areas [2], come with one critical disadvantage - reduced or completely non-existent comprehensibility on *how* they reach their results. Many GNN-specific methods have been developed to answer questions about both feature and structural importance [3]. When combined with the proposed pharmacophore representations, these methods could provide valuable insights to model users, however, their application to chemical data remains largely unexplored. We have developed two GNN models, a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) and a Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN), trained on 2D pharmacophore representations of small molecules, for drug activity prediction. We compare the results against shallow models, and against GNNs trained on traditionally used atomic representations of molecules. Using a selection of techniques, we aim to explain results of such models. We plan to obtain both local (molecule-level) and global (model-level) explanations, allowing us to analyse individual predictions as well as overarching model behaviour, which will help us to identify the sources of errors and refine our models accordingly.

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Coarse-Grained Simulations of the Bacterial Ribosome Using the MARTINI model

Josef Cikhart¹, Michal H. Kolář¹

¹ Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic

Ribosomes are essential biomolecular nanomachines responsible for protein synthesis, a fundamental process in all known organisms. Our knowledge about the structure of the ribosome has improved dramatically since the advent of modern analytical methods such as cryogenic electron microscopy (cryo-EM) or X-ray crystallography. However, the dynamics of the ribosome, just as crucial to the biological function as the structure, remain less understood.

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are able to provide detailed insights into the dynamics of molecular systems. Indeed, all-atom MD simulations have become a hallmark method in such studies of biomolecules. However, the high computational cost and the short achievable timestep for the numerical integration of Newton's equation of motion limits their feasibility for studying large biomolecular complexes such as the ribosome on biologically relevant timescales. Despite the posed challenge, several studies have emerged simulating an entire ribosome^{1,2}.

One possible way to overcome these difficulties is coarse-graining, which replaces groups of atoms with beads parametrized by a coarse-grained force field. Thus, reducing the number of degrees of freedom and enabling simulations of larger systems over longer timescales through well-established mathematical and physical principles. In this study, we investigate the parameters of the MARTINI 2 force field³ for CG simulations of the bacterial ribosome. Through a series of simulation setups, we assess the so-called elastic networks. The elastic networks are an additional scaffold added to the CG model, which improves the tertiary structure of protein and RNA within the CG free energy landscape.

Our results indicate that all the simulated CG elastic networks effectively preserve the ribosome's structure, including its components, when compared to the cryo-EM model. In addition, we compare structural and dynamical quantities with an all-atom simulation reference¹. From this comparison, we further demonstrate that while the CG systems yield a more compact and less flexible ribosome, the fine tuning of the elastic network parameters has a considerable effect on the alignment of the dynamics with atomistic models. These findings provide a detailed protocol for coarse-grained simulations of the ribosome and evaluate the areas of dynamical studies of large biomolecules the CG model is best applicable for.

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Design of antibodies and enzymes using neural networks

David Příhoda^{1,2}

¹ Department of Informatics and Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic.

² Applied Research and Innovation, MSD Czech Republic s.r.o, Prague, Czech Republic.

In this talk, based on my dissertation, I will explore how machine learning can advance drug discovery and drug manufacturing. First, I will describe antibody design with BioPhi, our open-source platform for streamlining antibody humanization and humanness evaluation. Leveraging deep learning and the diversity of natural antibody repertoires, our Sapiens language model predicts optimal humanizing mutations, and the OASis score provides a quantitative measure of an antibody's humanness. Next, I will explain how we use publicly available protein language models to optimize enzymes used in drug manufacturing. Finally, I will offer practical insights on applying machine learning to proteins, demonstrating the transformative potential of these approaches in accelerating drug discovery.

De Novo Drug Design: Combining Pharmacophore Modeling, 3D Shape Matching, and Generative AI

Jozef Fülöp¹, Martin Šícho¹, Daniel Svozil^{1,2}

¹ Department of Informatics and Chemistry & CZ-OPENSSCREEN: National Infrastructure for Chemical Biology, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic.

² CZ-OPENSSCREEN: National Infrastructure for Chemical Biology, Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic.

Recent studies show that shape-based generative models can enable scaffold hopping and diverse lead discovery via reinforcement learning [1], while voxel-based shape autoencoders successfully uncover novel scaffolds guided by 3D shape inputs[2]. Pharmacophore modeling that exploits the shape and color of Tanimoto scores (e.g., in ROCS) has proven valuable for identifying compounds that share key three-dimensional features, even when they differ structurally, thus moving beyond close analogs [3]. Here, we present an integrated pipeline that combines shape-based pharmacophore modeling with pharmacophoric characteristics (color) to capture both geometry and functional site alignments, along with a de novo generative model (DrugEx) that proposes new structures that meet both high Tanimoto shape/color similarity and synthetic accessibility [4]. Given its involvement in inflammation and tumor metastasis, we use the chemokine receptor CCR2 as a case study, where allosteric modulation offers a promising therapeutic strategy [5]. Our approach employs state-of-the-art commercial tools (ROCS and OMEGA) [3] alongside open-source frameworks (RDKit [6] and CDPKit [7]) to ensure robust and reproducible workflows, delivering an open-source solution that provides an alternative to commercial software. Finally, a comparison of commercial and open-source solutions for shape overlays and conformer generation reveals trade-offs in speed and optimization, especially for large-scale libraries, illustrating the potential of our integrated pipeline for lead discovery.

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Embedding-Based Molecular Dynamics for Similarity Search

Gorta Samuel

MUNI

Molecular dynamics simulations have long relied on classical coordinate representations of molecular systems to study their structural and dynamical properties. However, these representations often suffer from inefficiencies in capturing high-dimensional and non-Euclidean molecular conformations. In this study, we propose an alternative approach using learned embeddings instead of classical Cartesian or internal coordinates. By leveraging machine learning techniques, such as variational autoencoders (VAEs) and VAMPnets, we map molecular structures onto a lower-dimensional latent space that preserves essential physical and chemical features.

Beyond improving efficiency and representation, this latent space enables similarity searches among molecules based on the trajectories they explore. By defining molecular similarity in terms of the proximity of their embeddings in the latent space, we can compare dynamical behaviors rather than just static structures. This facilitates applications such as identifying functionally related biomolecules, clustering molecular conformations, and enhancing molecular design strategies by leveraging trajectory-based similarity measures.

Capturing Protein Dynamics and Its Determinants Using Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Faraneh Haddadi^{1,2*}, Joan Planas-Iglesias^{1,2}, Jiri Damborsky^{1,2}, Stanislav Mazurenko^{1,2}

¹Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

²International Clinical Research Centre, St. Anne's Hospital, Brno, Czech Republic

*Email: faraneh.haddadi@recetox.muni.cz

Molecular dynamics (MD), relying on physical laws of motion, predicts the movement of atoms and molecules over time, playing a key role in understanding the physical properties of materials and biological systems like proteins, DNA, and small molecules. However, the complexity of these systems makes it difficult to analyze their behavior using traditional methods alone such as visual inspection or unsupervised clustering. Machine learning (ML) and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) offer powerful tools for tackling this challenge by enabling the analysis of large, complex datasets, uncovering patterns and relationships, and making predictions [1]. XAI provides a transparent and interpretable framework for understanding ML model outputs, which is especially valuable in scientific research. Methods like layer-wise relevance propagation (LRP) help researchers to identify the most influential input features driving predictions made on a model, offering insights into the underlying factors affecting the results. This study aims to determine whether XAI can capture the dynamic determinants of a selected group of luciferases, RLuc8, AncFT, and Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, and to compare these findings with experimental results. We are developing an XAI-based method leveraging MD data and autoencoder architecture. Identifying key dynamic regions provides insights that could be leveraged for enzyme design and optimization, facilitating rational engineering strategies. Notably, the method highlights the L9- α 4- α 5' fragment as a critical region for dynamics prediction, aligning with previous experimental and computational findings that emphasize its importance in the structural behavior of these proteins [2].

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Mean-Field Approximation of AdEx Network with Synaptic Short-Term Depression

Pavel Haman^{1,2}, Ján Antolík¹, Alain Destexhe²

¹ Department of Software Engineering, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

² Paris-Saclay University, Institute of Neuroscience (NeuroPSI), CNRS, Saclay, France

Biologically plausible models of neural networks are essential for understanding the computational principles underlying visual processing in the primary visual cortex (V1). While detailed spiking network models capture the rich dynamics of neural activity and directly model biological phenomena, their computational complexity limits their utility for large-scale simulations and theoretical analysis. Mean-field approximations provide a complementary analytical framework, but current approaches often rely on mathematical assumptions that neglect crucial biological observations on the network level or rely on simplified neuron models.

This study extends existing mean-field methodologies for Adaptive Exponential (AdEx) neuron networks to incorporate short-term synaptic depression, following the theoretical work of Destexhe and colleagues. By explicitly addressing for the dynamics of synaptic resources, our approach provides a more comprehensive representation of neural network behavior. We demonstrate that directly incorporating synaptic plasticity significantly improves the accuracy of the transfer function when compared to single neuron simulations with dynamic synapses. Our validation approach compares network-level simulations against our enhanced mean-field approximations of AdEx neural networks with short-term synaptic plasticity.

The incorporation of short-term depression into mean-field approximations represents an important step toward developing more biologically realistic models of cortical processing. This improvement enables more biologically plausible analysis of neural dynamics while maintaining computational tractability. Our ongoing work focuses on fully validating the model against network-level simulations and extending the framework toward a multi-layer, multi-column mean-field model of V1. This research ultimately aims to develop a mean-field approximation tightly coupled to a large-scale spiking network of V1, thus, preserving a direct link to biological mechanisms while providing deeper insights into the functional organization and computational principles of the visual cortex through mathematically tractable yet biologically informed models.

New reference sequence and transcriptomic atlas of the maize B chromosome

Hloušková Lucie^{1,2}, Tulpová Zuzana¹, Svačina Radim¹, Holušová Kateřina¹, Petr Cápál¹, Navrátilová Pavla¹, Karafiátová Miroslava¹ and Bartoš Jan^{1*}

¹Institute of Experimental Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Centre of Plant Structural and Functional Genomics, Šlechtitelů 31, Olomouc, 779 00, Czech Republic

²Department of Cell Biology and Genetics, Palacký University, Olomouc, Czech Republic

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most important crops. It serves as an established model for biological research and the maize B chromosome has been studied for many decades. However, the gene expression of the maize B chromosome across different plant tissues has not been thoroughly described. Here we present the improved reference sequence of the maize B chromosome with updated gene annotation and comprehensive transcriptomic atlas of the maize B chromosome across the entire life cycle of the maize plant. For the improvement of the reference sequence we integrated advanced sequencing technologies, including long-read sequencing, Hi-C library construction, and optical mapping. Using RNA-seq and gene expression analysis we identified B-chromosome specific genes expressed in various developmental stages and plant organs. Further, the effect of B chromosome on the expression of A-chromosomal complement was investigated.

Shedding light on the secrets of NanoLuc, its mechanism, and allosteric behaviour

Horáčková J.^{1,2}, Nemergut M.^{1,2}, Pluskal D.¹, Šustrová T.¹, Marek M.^{1,2}, Bednář D.^{1,2}

¹ Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5, Bld. C13, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic

² International Clinical Research Center, St. Anne's University Hospital Brno, Pekařská 53, 656 91 Brno, Czech Republic

NanoLuc luciferase, a small enzyme renowned for its exceptionally bright bioluminescence, has found widespread applications in biotechnology and biomedicine since being designed in 2012 [1]. However, the mystery behind NanoLuc's light-emitting reaction, crucial for developing next-generation bioluminescent systems, remained unsolved. In this study, we made significant progress in understanding NanoLuc's mechanism by combining various laboratory and computational techniques, including crystallography, kinetic measurements, molecular docking, and molecular dynamics simulations with enhanced sampling.

One of the most intriguing features of NanoLuc is its small size, consisting of just 171 amino acid residues, in contrast to luciferases from sea pansy *Renilla reniformis* (311 residues) and firefly *Photinus pyralis* (550 residues). We confirmed that NanoLuc is monomeric in solution but can also crystallize as a homotetramer under certain conditions. We have also identified two distinct binding sites (Fig. 1) for the substrate molecule: the catalytic site, which is buried in the core of the NanoLuc monomer, and an allosteric binding pocket shaped on the oligomerization interface of NanoLuc crystals [2]. Importantly, we have demonstrated that introducing mutations in the allosteric site can enhance the bioluminescent reaction occurring in the active site.

Figure 1. Two distinct substrate binding sites of NanoLuc – the catalytic site (left) and the allosteric site (right).

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StreaMD tool for high-throughput automated molecular dynamics simulations and its validation

A. Ivanova¹, O. Mokshyna², P. Polishchuk¹

1 Institute of Molecular and Translational Medicine, Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry, Palacký University and University Hospital in Olomouc, Hnevotinska 5, 77900 Olomouc, Czech Republic

2 Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Flemingovo náměstí 542/2, 160 00 Praha 6, Czech Republic

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and binding free energy calculations are widely used in computational chemistry and molecular biology. This study presents the implementation and validation of a StreaMD tool designed to automate molecular dynamics simulations and to run them for a large number of systems simultaneously [1]. The tool runs system preparation, starts or extends MD simulations, performs trajectory analysis, and computes MMG(P)BSA binding free energies, along with detailed protein-ligand interaction analyses. The pipeline supports diverse systems, such as protein, protein-cofactors, protein-ligand, and protein-ligand-cofactors complexes in explicit water environments. By utilizing the Dask Python library the tool supports parallelization and distributed computing across a network of servers via SSH connections independent from a particular scheduler. The tool enables GPU-accelerated computations, offering a substantial reduction in processing time.

For validation, we ran 10 ns simulations and calculated the GBSA energies by using the final 5 ns of the 10th ns trajectory for 624 complexes sourced from the Greenidge dataset [2], 166 molecules of human β -secretase 1 (UniProt ID: P56817), 63 molecules of human α -thrombin (UniProt ID: P00734), and 51 molecules of bovine trypsin (UniProt ID: P00760). The resulting Pearson correlation coefficients between GBSA energies and experimental activity values for molecules that met the proposed convergence criteria (average RMSD ≤ 5 Å and standard deviation of RMSD ≤ 0.5 Å) were -0.69 for the Greenidge, -0.63 for the β -secretase 1, -0.69 for the α -thrombin, and -0.65 for the trypsin datasets. The StreaMD and MM-GBSA methods were applied in an advanced high-throughput screening process during the Critical Assessment of Computational Hit-Finding Experiments (CACHE) Challenge #1 competition as a final ranking procedure to select 150 molecules from 900 candidates obtained from the previous ranking stages. The achieved hit rate was $\sim 10\%$ (8 compounds were active out of 82 studied ones). To estimate the scalability of StreaMD we compared single-node, multiple-node, and GPU-single-node modes. We found that the GPU acceleration provided approximately a 200% speedup compared to a node with 128 CPUs and showed the best performance settings.

The tool is available as an open-source package at <https://github.com/ci-lab-cz/streamd/tree/master>.

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MolMeDB - Molecules on Membranes Database

Jakub Juračka^{1,2}, Kateřina Storchmannová¹, Dominik Martinát¹, Václav Bazgier¹, Karel Berka¹

¹ Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, Czech Republic

² Department of Computer Sciences, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, Czech Republic

Biological membranes are natural barriers to cells. They play a key role in cell life and the pharmacokinetics of drug-like small molecules. A small molecule can pass through the membranes in two ways: via passive diffusion or actively via membrane transport proteins. There is a huge amount of data available about interactions of the small molecules with membranes and about interactions among the small molecules and the transporters.

MolMeDB (molmedb.upol.cz) is a comprehensive and interactive database of interactions of small molecules with membranes.¹ From the start, we have collected data about partitioning and penetration of the small molecules crossing the membranes. Recently, we have expanded our area of interest to include interactions of small molecules with transporters and ion channels. Nowadays, more than 930,000 interactions for almost 500,000 molecules are available in MolMeDB.

The data within the MolMeDB is collected from scientific papers, our in-house calculations (COSMOmic/COSMOperm²), and obtained by data mining from several databases (e.g. ChEMBL, PubChem, The IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY³). Data in the MolMeDB are fully searchable and browsable by name, SMILES, membrane, method, transporter, or dataset, and we offer collected data openly for further reuse. Also, the content of the database is available via REST API and the RDF model of MolMeDB (docs.molmedb.upol.cz).

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Mapping Protein Language: Exploring Amino Acid Functionality through Machine Learning

Filip Kapral¹, Václav Hanžl¹, Vojtěch Spiwok¹

¹ Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology - University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague

Language is a structured system that allows humans to exchange information using sentences and words. Words carry meaning, and their sequence in a sentence determines how information is interpreted. The same principle applies to a universal language understood by all of us - the language of protein sequences, which has a much smaller vocabulary but is still rich in sentence diversity. Homonyms are words that share the same spelling but have different meanings (functions), such as *mean* (as in average) versus *mean* (to signify) or *bow* (a weapon) versus *bow* (the act of bending forward). Similarly, each amino acid in a protein primary structure functions as a "word" within a long clause. Depending on its context (i.e., neighbouring residues), an amino acid can take on different roles. For instance, histidine can be a charged residue on a protein surface, a specialized component of a catalytic triad, or a metal-chelating residue. With recent advances in machine learning, we can now map amino acid functionality in human proteins. ESM-2 (Evolutionary Scale Modelling) is a tool designed to model and extract information from protein sequences at the residue level. Each amino acid residue can be transformed into an n-dimensional vector, which is then reduced to 2D for visualization. These mapped points are linked to 3D protein structures to facilitate further investigation. Our goal is to integrate interactive elements into this mapping system, enabling users to explore proteins of interest and deepen their understanding of structure-based functionality.

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Tissue-restricted antigen-like expression of endogenous retroviruses in the thymus supports their role in negative selection

M. Klianitskaya^{1,2}, S. Sinitsyn³, J. Reiniš², M. Vincendeau⁴, D. Frishman³, D. Filipp⁵, J. Pačes^{1,2}

¹ Department of Informatics and Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic

² Laboratory of Genomics and Bioinformatics, Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

³ Associate Professorship of Bioinformatics, TUM School of Life Sciences, Technical University of Munich

⁴ Endogenous retroviruses group, Institute of Virology, Helmholtz Munich

⁵ Laboratory of Immunobiology, Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

Endogenous retroviruses (ERVs) are remnants of ancient viral infections that have been part of the host genome for millions of years. Despite their viral origin, ERV-derived proteins and RNA are found in healthy tissues without triggering an immune response. This raises a fundamental question: why does the immune system tolerate these foreign elements? A likely explanation is that ERVs are incorporated into immune tolerance mechanisms, preventing autoimmunity against their expression products. Since immune tolerance is established in the thymus through the negative selection of autoreactive T cells, we hypothesize that ERVs are expressed in medullary thymic epithelial cells (mTECs) and presented as self-antigens.

To test this, we analyzed single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) data from human and mouse thymic tissues, focusing on mTECs—specialized cells that train T cells by expressing a broad set of tissue-restricted antigens (TRAs). Our results show that ERVs are actively transcribed in mTECs following a pattern similar to TRAs: the number of expressed ERV loci is significantly higher in mTECs compared to other thymic cells. We also found that younger ERV subfamilies are more transcriptionally active, and many ERV loci overlap with long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), some of which are linked to different pathological conditions. These findings were consistent in both humans and mice, pointing to an evolutionarily conserved role for ERVs in thymic selection.

This study provides the first locus-specific analysis of ERV expression in mTECs and suggests that ERVs may actively contribute to immune tolerance. By exposing developing T cells to ERV-derived antigens, the thymus might prevent autoimmunity against these elements later in life. Our findings challenge the view of ERVs as inactive genomic fossils and highlight their potential role in shaping immune regulation, with implications for autoimmune diseases and immune responses to ERV reactivation in disease states.

Variational Autoencoder Latent Spaces as a Powerful Framework for Protein Evolution and Design

Pavel Kohout^{1,2,#}, Michal Vasina^{1,2,#}, Marika Majerova^{1,2}, Veronika Novakova^{1,2}, Jiri Damborsky^{1,2}, David Bednar^{1,2}, Martin Marek^{1,2}, Zbynek Prokop^{1,2}, Stanislav Mazurenko^{1,2}

¹ Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

² International Clinical Research Centre, St. Anne's Hospital, Brno, Czech Republic

These authors contributed equally. e-mail address: pavel.kohout@recetox.muni.cz

The vast sequence space of proteins presents a significant challenge in protein design, as only a tiny fraction of possible sequences are functional. Evolutionary principles help navigate this immense space by focusing on protein family-related sites and mutations, effectively constraining design efforts to functionally relevant regions. Ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) is a powerful method for evolutionary-based protein design, using homologous sequences in a multiple sequence alignment and an inferred phylogenetic tree to reconstruct ancestral nodes. However, ASR remains a labour-intensive process, requiring numerous manual steps. Generative machine learning models provide a promising avenue for designing enhanced proteins by leveraging techniques from natural language processing to decipher essential evolutionary patterns from large datasets of amino acid sequences. While generative models have been helpful for protein design, there remains a limited understanding of introducing beneficial mutations without disrupting function [1]. On the other hand, complex protein evolution data provides a powerful tool for extracting meaningful information automatically.

This study introduces the latent spaces of variational autoencoders (VAEs) and sampling strategies to generate variants resembling ancestral sequences from multiple sequence alignments of specific protein families. To this end, we optimized the VAE architecture to capture evolutionary dependencies in the latent space geometry. We found two dimensions and a single dense layer sufficient to reconstruct close ancestral variants of given protein families. We employed sampling strategies of sequence mutagenesis, latent space evolutionary trajectories, and multi-objective optimization. We used the evolutionary trajectory strategy on the haloalkane dehalogenases protein family and obtained variants with increased activity and stability [2]. Building upon this collected high-quality experimental data, we used structure and inverse fold predictors to examine protein foldability scores. We designed a sampling strategy aimed at generating sequences that jointly had high foldability scores and possessed traits of ancestral sequences, thus potentially improving the success rate of generated variants. The VAE strategy is available as an interactive module of the FireProtASR 2.0 tool: <https://loschmidt.chemi.muni.cz/fireprotasr2/>.

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Deoxyribozyme discovery driven by NGS sequencing

Jaroslav Kurfurst^{1,2}, Edward A. Curtis¹,

¹Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the CAS

² Department of Informatics and Chemistry UCT Prague

The SELEX protocol is a powerful tool for exploring the functional potential of nucleic acids. Large pools of randomly synthesized DNA or RNA molecules are incubated with various potential substrates. Active molecules are separated from the inactive ones, isolated and the process is repeated until a strong enough signal of activity is detected. Next-gen sequencing of the reaction product provides valuable information about selected functional motifs. As the patterns hidden in the data can be very convoluted, we develop new methods to be able to understand the important sequence features and optimize selected sequences. We use these results to complement our research in the wet-lab.

Detection of positive selection in songbird spermatozoa

Lukáš Cakl¹, Pavel Stopka¹, Tomáš Albrecht^{1,2}, Jiří Reif³, Stephen Schlebusch¹, Radka Reifová¹

¹ Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague

² Institute of Vertebrate Biology, Czech Academy of Sciences

³ Institute of Environmental Studies, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague

Spermatozoa show very high variability in morphology and performance between species. Those differences are mostly driven by postcopulatory sexual selection and/or sexual antagonism. The molecular mechanisms underlying this variation are, however, still poorly understood. Here, we have investigated the molecular evolution of proteins expressed in spermatozoa across passerines, the largest group of birds consisting of over 6500 species. Passerine spermatozoa show a unique helical shape and swim by rapidly rotating around their longitudinal axis. Their morphology is also highly diverse among the species. Out of the 940 genes whose protein products have been detected in spermatozoa, we have found 22 which are evolving under positive selection. Gene ontology analysis has revealed an overrepresentation of biological process and molecular functions related to microtubule-based movement and microtubule motor activity respectively. Our results bring the first insight into the molecular mechanisms which might drive sperm evolution in passerines.

PySPRESSO: Simple Python Pipeline for Multi-Batch LCMS Data processing

Jan Machán¹, Lukáš Najdekr¹, Richard Masař¹

¹ Institute of Molecular and Translational Medicine; Hněvotínská 1333/5; Olomouc 779 00; Czech Republic

In this work, we present an open-source off-line Python pipeline that is designed to simplify the processing of large "multi-batch" LCMS data. This tool includes various filters, correction methods, and statistical tools that allow users to customize settings to the specific needs of their data. We conceived the pipeline as an all-in-one solution for data processing following the use of "peak-picking" software such as MZmine or Compound Discoverer. Pipeline effectively addresses the problems of batch effect and other analytical errors. In addition to data processing, the main advantages are the ability to generate images suitable for presentations or publications and the subsequent creation of a reporting PDF file that allows users to follow each process applied onto the data step by step. The ability to work off-line with "multi-batch" LCMS data, including those with many missing values, is particularly useful for cases of confidential or excessively large files that are not suitable for uploading to popular online tools. The user can run the workflow locally and interpret the data very quickly by themselves. The code of the pipeline is written entirely in Python, ensuring accessibility and easy implementation of new filters and data transformations. With Python as the main machine learning language, it is also ready to integrate various AI models for feature prediction, data classification, or other correction methods such as SERRF, for example. This pipeline can contribute not only to accelerate data analysis and evaluation, but also to improve reproducibility and unify approaches across scientific teams thanks to its fully accessible code.

Knot or Not? Looking for Knotting Patterns in Proteins

Eva Maršálová^{1,2}, Denisa Šrámková^{1,2}, Agata Perlińska³, Maciej Sikora³, Joanna Sulkowska³, Petr Šimeček¹

¹ Central European Institute of Technology, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

² National Centre for Biomolecular Research, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

³ Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Poland

Two decades ago, an intriguing phenomenon emerged: proteins can contain knots in their polypeptide backbone, making it impossible to completely untangle them by pulling from both ends. Since this discovery, numerous knotted proteins have been identified. However, the processes governing knot formation, the functional implications, and the amino acid patterns responsible for knot creation remain unclear. Recent advancements in machine learning and natural language processing have enabled the prediction of protein 3D structures with remarkable precision, exemplified by models like AlphaFold2. AlphaFold DB, with open access to over 200 million protein structure predictions, has unlocked the potential for computational analysis of these newly predicted structures and search for those containing a knot.

We examined the AlphaFold DB to create a robust dataset of knotted and unknotted proteins. Using this dataset, we developed a machine learning model capable of accurately predicting the presence of knots in protein structures based solely on their amino acid sequences (<https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.4998>). While the model exhibits high accuracy in predicting a protein's knot status, it does not directly provide a biological explanation or pinpoint the specific regions contributing to knot formation. To address this, we applied a custom interpretation sequence patching technique to several protein families to uncover the knotting patterns learned by the model. When analyzing these sequence motifs within families, we found that the patterns closely correspond to the functional sites of the protein families. Further analysis revealed that, in the examined families, the knotted topology is strictly conserved in functional proteins, whereas proteins from the same families that lack knots are typically non-functional fragments missing a significant portion of the knot core—and consequently, the family-specific sequence knotting pattern.

To further investigate knotting patterns and bridge the limited diversity of knotted protein families found in nature, we sought to expand the spectrum of knotted configurations. We explored computational tools for novel protein generation (represented by RFDiffusion + ProteinMPNN and EvoDiff), and monitored the knotting status of the generated proteins. Our findings reveal that the artificially generated proteins closely mimic the natural occurrence of knotted proteins, with a comparable percentage exhibiting non-trivial topologies. Additionally, we identified several knot types previously unobserved in natural proteins. By integrating all approaches, we compiled a more diverse dataset of knotted and unknotted structures, comprising nearly 100,000 proteins. Based on this dataset, we plan to combine a custom-trained model with a diffusion-based protein backbone model (FoldingDiff) to guide protein generation toward either knotted or unknotted topology and observe the occurred changes.

Decoding the Mchare Banana Genome: A Complete Assembly for Structural and Evolutionary Studies

Simona Martikánová¹, Zuzana Tulpová¹, Allan Brown³, Rony Swennen^{3,4}, Eva Hřibová¹

¹ Institute of Experimental Botany, Centre of Plant Structural and Functional Genomics, Olomouc, Czech Republic

² International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Banana Breeding, PO Box 447 Arusha, Tanzania

³ International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Kampala P.O. Box 7878, Uganda

⁴ Division of Crop Biotechnics, Laboratory of Tropical Crop Improvement, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, 3001 Leuven, Belgium

Mchare bananas (AA genome) are an important group of diploid cultivars cultivated in East and Central Africa, known for their unique genetic background. Recent studies have confirmed their hybrid origin and complex evolution and highlighted their distinct genome structure. Despite their significance, Mchare bananas remain highly susceptible to diseases, and their hybrid origin, parthenocarpy and seed sterility pose challenges for breeding programs. A deeper understanding of their genome structure is essential for improving cultivars through molecular breeding. Moreover, contribution of Mchare to the origin of the other autotriploid banana clones will shed light on the evolution of the most important export banana clone Cavendish (AAA genome).

To address this, we assembled a telomere-to-telomere (T2T) genome of the Mchare banana clone ‘Huti White’ using a combination of PacBio HiFi and Oxford Nanopore long reads, coupled with Bionano optical mapping. This approach enabled to resolve individual subgenomes (haplotypes) and provided insight into large-scale structural variations. Automatic annotation enhanced with RNA-Seq data resulted in identification of 72 398 high-confidence genes that were used to analyze important collinear regions and evolutionary relationships within *Musa* and *Musaceae* family. Additionally, the phased genome assembly of Mchare enabled to identify chromosomes and their structure in Mchare x ‘Calcutta4’ F1 hybrid clones.

This fully assembled and annotated genome represents a critical resource for studying Mchare evolution, structural genome variation, and molecular breeding, paving the way for the development of more resilient and productive banana cultivars.

Biological ontology research as a playground for wannabe philosophers and logicians in our midst

Dominik Martinát

Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic

Ontologies help create interoperability between individual fields as they define the relationships between data and concepts within individual domains. Established ontologies describe proteins and protein research, such as the BioAssays ontology. However, there is no ontology focused on biological membrane research. We are developing an ontology describing membrane models and their relationship to real-life lipid membranes, which are subjects of biological and pharmaceutical research as barriers, drug targets, metabolic sites, and more. And dare I say, it is quite an experience!

While my expectations were modest when I started in this field, I have found it to be fascinating and exciting, and I would like to share. Ontology development includes many components: Coding? Check! Logic? Absolutely! Philosophy? We've got you covered, chief! Biology? Well, we need something to model knowledge about. If any of these pique your interest, I invite you to explore with me. Perhaps you'll find your new scientific home here too.

Applying the Bioarchaeological Analyses to Reconstruct Origins and Mobility of Human Populations in the Late Bronze and Early Iron Age Central Europe: Project Introduction

Adam Nógell^{1,3}, Maciej Chylenski², Jan Pačes^{1,3} Anna Juras² and Edvard Ehler^{1*}

¹ Laboratory of Genomics and Bioinformatics, Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Vídeňská 1083, 142 00 Prague 4, Czech Republic

² Ancient DNA Laboratory, Institute of Human Biology & Evolution, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, ul. Uniwersytetu Poznańskiego 6, 61-614 Poznań, Poland

³ Department of Informatics and Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

* corresponding author, email: edvard.ehler@img.cas.cz

During the Late Bronze Age and Early Iron Age, the widespread practice of cremation in Central Europe—characterized by the Urnfield phenomenon—has led to significant gaps in our understanding of the genetic history of the Lusatian, Knovíz-Štítary, and Hallstatt cultures. To address this gap, we have assembled a unique collection of human skeletal samples, primarily from biritual archaeological sites where inhumations predominate, located in Upper Silesia (Poland), and Moravia and Bohemia regions (Czech Republic).

Our primary aim is to elucidate the genetic backgrounds of populations associated with these cultures, thereby addressing questions regarding their origins and relationship. In addition, we will assess gene flow between populations linked to the Lusatian and Knovíz-Štítary cultures, exploring the extent to which genetic patterns align with the cultural differences observed in Urnfield-related phenomena. Furthermore, we will investigate potential migrations within Lusatian culture populations from regions favouring inhumation practices. Kinship analysis among densely sampled sites, including common and multiple burial pits, will offer further insights into marriage patterns, social structures, and inheritance practices in these populations. To achieve these objectives, we will employ a multidisciplinary approach, integrating ancient DNA (aDNA) analysis, radiocarbon dating, and isotopic measurements (strontium and oxygen isotopes). Specifically, we plan to analyse over 160 individuals for aDNA, and more than 70 individuals for isotopic analysis (radiocarbon dating, and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$).

This report introduces the research project focused on Bronze Age–Iron Age transition and human populations in Central Europe, as well as the first results from sequencing screening of majority of our target samples. These results will significantly advance the field of bioarchaeology by providing new insights into migration patterns, gene flow, and population structure during the pivotal period in Central European prehistory. Our research will fill critical gaps in our understanding of the genetic and cultural dynamics of populations associated with the Lusatian, Knovíz-Štítary, and Hallstatt cultures, contributing to broader discussions about human mobility and cultural exchange in prehistory.

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IDENTIFICATION AND ANALYSIS OF PROMOTERS IN THE BARLEY GENOME

Simon Pavlu^a, Sarvesh Nikumbh^b, Martin Kovačik^a, Tadaichi An^c, Boris Lenhard^b, Pavla Navratilova^a, Hana Simkova^a

^a *Institute of Experimental Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Šlechtitelů 31, 77900, Olomouc, Czech Republic*

^b *MRC London Institute of Medical Sciences, Hammersmith Hospital Campus, Du Cane Road, London, W12 0NN*

^c *DNAFORM Precision Gene Technologies, 230-0046 Yokohama, Kanagawa, Japan*

Precise localization and dissection of gene promoters are key to understanding transcriptional gene regulation and to successful bioengineering applications. As a diploid species with a highly complete reference genome and established transgenesis protocols, barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) serves as a convenient model for studying promoter architecture in Triticeae crops.

To delineate and characterize promoters across three stages of barley embryo development, we employed Cap Analysis of Gene Expression (CAGE), which enabled precise genome-wide mapping of transcription start sites (TSSs), and quantification of transcription initiation events at the cost comparable to RNA-seq. Our analysis revealed numerous discrepancies between annotated (MorexV3) and CAGE-detected TSSs. We also highlighted alternative transcription initiation events, some of which are developmental stage-specific or influencing regulatory or protein-coding sequences. The application of a novel core promoter sequence clustering approach and integration of genome-wide epigenomic datasets, together with gene ontology enrichment analysis further delineated the chromatin environments and functional roles of genes associated with distinct promoter categories.

The generated CAGE datasets, mapped to MorexV3 barley reference genome, were integrated with published RNA-seq and newly generated epigenome and interactome data in our internal JBrowse-based browser, which will serve as a valuable genomic resource for the barley community.

The project was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (grant number 21-18794S).

Metabolic Flux and Transcriptomic Analysis of Metachronous Colorectal Liver Metastasis

Bhavana Hemantha Rao¹, Karolina Šeborová^{1,2}, Václav Liška^{1,3}, Ondřej Vyčítal^{1,3}, Ondřej Fiala^{1,4}, Pavel Souček^{1,2}, Viktor Hlaváč^{1,2}

¹Biomedical Center, Faculty of Medicine in Pilsen, Charles University, Pilsen, Czech Republic

²Toxicogenomics Unit, National Institute of Public Health, Prague, Czech Republic

³Department of Surgery, Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital in Pilsen, Charles University, Pilsen, Czech Republic

⁴Department of Oncology and Radiotherapeutics, Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital in Pilsen, Charles University, Pilsen, Czech Republic

Metabolic alterations are well-known characteristics of colorectal cancer, although they remain poorly understood, particularly in metachronous liver metastasis (mCLM). The present study explores the metabolic pathways in mCLM using the METAbolic Flux balance analysis (MetaFlux) package in R and the normalized transcriptomic data from RNA sequencing of fresh frozen metastasis and their adjacent liver tissue samples. The MetaFlux framework calculates the metabolic fluxes from gene expression data. This study aimed for known key metabolic factors in fatty acid oxidation, creatinine metabolism, and fructose metabolism, all of which are vital energy supplies found solely in liver metastases rather than primary tumors or other metastatic locations.

We found a significant dysregulation in metabolites involved in carnitine transport and fructose-mannose metabolism, indicating that mCLM tumors may rewire their energy utilization to promote growth and survival. The study further investigated the transcriptional regulation of these metabolic changes using the mRNA co-expression analysis, which identified four clusters, of which genes from Cluster 1 were associated with the existing 142 metabolic pathways in MetaFlux. Several common pathways deregulated in tumors were identified by integrating the MetaFlux-derived pathways with Cluster 1, including the xenobiotics metabolism, drug metabolism, glycolysis/gluconeogenesis, tryptophan metabolism, and tricarboxylic acid cycle.

These findings demonstrate that the interaction between transcriptional regulation and metabolic flux in mCLM can provide insights into the modification of tumors' metabolism to survive in the liver microenvironment. This study sets a basis for future research into these metabolic pathways, which may lead to new treatment strategies in mCLM patients.

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Design of Enhanced Proteins through Protein Evolution Anticipation

Monika Rosinska^{1,3}, Rayyan Tariq Khan^{1,2}, Pavel Kohout^{1,2}, Milos Musil^{1,2,3}, Jiri Damborsky^{1,2}, Stanislav Mazurenko^{1,2,*} and David Bednar^{1,2,*}

¹ Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

² International Clinical Research Center, St. Anne's University Hospital Brno, Brno, Czech Republic

³ Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Information Technology, Brno University of Technology, Brno, Czech Republic

* Corresponding authors: jiri@chemi.muni.cz; mazurenko@mail.muni.cz, davidbednar1208@gmail.com

Analysis of protein evolution provides crucial insights into protein development and offers valuable guidance for designing their properties and exploring the vast sequence space. These analyses are usually done retrospectively utilising ancestral sequence reconstruction or back-to-consensus engineering. However, the Successor Sequence Predictor (SSP) introduces a novel approach by leveraging protein evolution information prospectively. Imitating traditional protein evolution analysis, SSP predicts future amino acid mutations based on the protein's evolutionary history.

For the desired protein sequence, the Successor Sequence Predictor functions in several steps: First, it generates a data set of homologous sequences utilising BLAST and preprocesses it, discarding sequences that are too similar ($\geq 90\%$ identity). Second, the remaining sequences are clustered, and phylogenetic trees are constructed from these clusters. Each phylogenetic tree contains the target sequence and one randomly selected sequence from each cluster. Third, ancestral sequences are reconstructed for each phylogenetic tree, and the sequences along the path between the target and the root are aligned. Fourth, using linear regression on selected amino acid indices, SSP predicts the successor sequence. Finally, evolving positions are identified based on changes in individual indices, and a specific mutation can be suggested if the indices agree on a particular amino acid change.

SSP was evaluated in the design of different protein properties for two proteins: Cold shock protein CspB and aminoglycoside 3'-phosphotransferase. For the former, SSP suggested 14 mutations that should enhance protein stability. Six mutations were stabilising and eight were neutral. Interestingly, none of the suggested mutations were compromising the folding free energy. In the case of aminoglycoside 3'-phosphotransferase, we observed an enhancement in activity through increased resistance to aminoglycosides. While random mutations resulted in an average resistance value of 0.82—indicating a decrease of resistance compared to the wild-type sequence (normalized to ~ 1)—SSP mutants exhibited an average value of 1.36, suggesting an increase in antibiotic resistance and therefore improved protein activity. The SSP codes are available on GitHub: <https://github.com/loschmidt/successor-sequence-predictor>. The method is also integrated into FireProtASR2, accessible at <https://loschmidt.chemi.muni.cz/fireprotasr2/>.

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Genetic diversity of turnip yellows virus and *Brassica* yellows virus across *Brassica* hosts

Archita Sahu^{1,2}, Emad Ibrahim², Adam Achs³, Peter Alaxin⁴, Miroslav Glasa^{3,4}, Jiban Kumar Kundu²

¹ Department of Crop Sciences and Agroforestry, The Faculty of Tropical Agri-Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic; sahua@ftz.czu.cz,

² Plant Virus and Vector Interactions, Czech Agrifood Research Center, Prague, Czech Republic; jiban.kumar@carc.cz; emad.ibrahim@carc.cz

³ Institute of Virology, Biomedical Research Centre, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia Miroslav.Glasa@savba.sk; adam.achs1@gmail.com,

⁴ Faculty of Natural Sciences, Institute of Biology and Biotechnology, University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius, Trnava, Slovakia, peter.alaxin13@gmail.com

Abstract- Turnip yellows virus (TuYV) is a significant pathogen affecting *Brassica species* globally, while a closely related virus, *Brassica* yellows virus (BrYV), has major impacts in Asia and Australia, particularly in Japan, South Korea, and China. This study aimed to assess the intra-species variability within these two poleroviruses (*Solemoviridae*), together with genetic diversity between TuYV and BrYV populations in *Brassica* hosts by analysing partial and complete nucleotide sequences. A total of 65 TuYV isolates and 26 BrYV isolates were aligned, revealing the clustering into four major groups using the Clustal W alignment tool, maximum composite likelihood and neighbour joining method with the Mega 11 and Geneious software. The analysis revealed that both BrYV and TuYV isolates share a common evolutionary origin. The clustering identifies three groups - TuYV1, TuYV2, TuYV3 predominantly composed of TuYV isolates, with exceptions of three BrYV isolates, namely BrYV-HQ, BrYV-NtabQJ and BrYV-Cheonsong. The fourth group, BrYV1 mainly consisted of BrYV isolates but also contained a cluster of five TuYV isolates. Within these four clusters, TuYV-3 exhibited the highest sequence similarity (approximately 95%), while TuYV1 and TuYV3 showed the highest mean distance (0.21) and TuYV2-BrYV-1 exhibited the lowest genetic distance (0.12). Further analysis focused on specific genomic regions including a portion of ORF2, NGR, ORF3a, and the partial CP and Readthrough domains. Additionally, three laboratory isolates of TuYV (two from the Czech Republic and one from Slovakia) were analysed by RT-PCR and Sanger sequencing of the PCR fragments. The analysis of these 797 bp partial genomic sequences, compared to global data using the maximum likelihood GTR model (1000 bootstrap replicates), revealed the clustering of the Czech and Slovak isolates into two major groups. One Czech isolate and the Slovak isolate clustered together, while the other Czech isolate was placed in different a distinct branch closer to the BrYV cluster. Both partial and full genomic data analyses showed higher intra-population genetic distance and differentiation in TuYV compared to BrYV, particularly in the Readthrough domain. This study highlights the genetic diversity and variability between TuYV and BrYV, providing valuable insights into their evolutionary dynamics and implications for disease management in *Brassica* crops worldwide.

How does protein flexibility affect protein-ligand binding behavior?

Vít Škrhák¹, David Hoksza¹

¹ Department of Software Engineering, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

Proteins, the primary drivers of biological systems, perform many of their functions by interacting with other molecules (ligands) at specialized regions called protein-ligand binding sites (LBSs). Identifying these sites is critical across various fields, from fundamental biology to biomedical applications. However, the dynamic nature of protein structures presents challenges for binding site prediction methods, particularly in the case of cryptic binding sites (CBSs), which require structural flexibility for the binding to form. Many prediction methods rely heavily on structure-based features, however, values of those features can vary significantly in regions with dynamic behavior such as CBSs. This variability could potentially limit the predictive power of such methods when detecting CBSs.

In this study, we investigate the behavior of features traditionally used in LBS prediction, comparing their properties in rigid binding sites versus cryptic ones. For this comparison, we leverage an existing CBS dataset published in our previous work and introduce a novel dataset of rigid binding sites, created using a similar methodology as the CBS dataset. Additionally, we explore novel features that, while not particularly relevant for detecting rigid binding sites, may prove beneficial in identifying cryptic binding sites.

By analyzing and contrasting these features, we aim to shed light on the factors driving flexibility in binding sites and to better understand the underlying dynamics of cryptic binding sites. While we do not aim to address the entire complexity of CBS prediction, our work seeks to provide valuable insights into feature behavior, ultimately identifying attributes that could enhance future CBS prediction methods. This foundational analysis serves as a step toward advancing tools for detecting these biologically significant sites.

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Refining Structure-Based Search in AlphaFold DB: Including pLDDT and PAE into AlphaFind

Terézia Slanináková¹, Eva Maršálková^{1,2}, Katarína Grešová, Aleš Křenek, Jaroslav Olša, Tomáš Pavlík, Matej Antol

¹ Department of Software Engineering, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

² Department of Cell Biology, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

³ Another institution

The AlphaFold Database (AFDB) represents a significant advancement in protein structure prediction, providing a wealth of structural data that holds immense potential for bioinformatics research. However, the sheer volume and complexity of this data necessitate the development of efficient tools for effective exploration and analysis. Inspired by the need for robust search capabilities, we developed AlphaFind (<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae397>), a structure-based similarity search system designed to navigate the vast landscape of the AFDB.

Despite its utility, AlphaFind currently does not account for the predicted Local Distance Difference Test (pLDDT) and Predicted Aligned Error (PAE) metrics, which are crucial for assessing the confidence of predicted structures. These metrics are particularly important as they correlate with disordered regions in protein structures. Parts of a protein chain with high pLDDT and low PAE can bias protein similarity searches, leading to inaccurate assessments of structural similarity. Equal weighting of ordered and disordered regions can artificially inflate or deflate TM-scores, potentially causing false positives or negatives in structure comparison results. For instance, the protein Q14676 (<https://alphafind.fi.muni.cz/search?q=Q14676>) exemplifies how low-confidence regions can skew search results. Therefore, incorporating these disordered regions into data representation is essential for improving search accuracy.

Simultaneously, there has been a surge in protein domain data of AFDB produced by The Encyclopedia of Domains (<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adq4946>).

In the poster: “Refining Structure-Based Search in AlphaFold DB: Including pLDDT and PAE into AlphaFind”, we outline two approaches to processing AFDB data that leverages pLDDT and PAE metrics in a domain-agnostic manner. We contrast this approach to the data processing reliant on the domain identification with TED. Each method is run through the search, and we discuss the differences in outcomes.

Our findings underscore the importance of integrating confidence metrics into structure-based search systems, paving the way for more precise and reliable similarity search on protein structures.

ChannelsDB 2.0: A Comprehensive Database of Protein Tunnels and Pores in AlphaFold Era

Anna Špačková¹, Ondřej Vávra^{2,3}, Tomáš Raček^{4,5}, Václav Bazgier¹, David Sehnal^{4,5}, Jiří Damborský^{2,3}, Radka Svobodová^{4,5,*}, David Bednář^{2,3,*}, Karel Berka^{1,*}

¹ Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University, tř. 17. listopadu 12, 771 46 Olomouc, Czech Republic

² Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic

³ International Clinical Research Center, St. Anne's University Hospital Brno, Pekařská 53, 656 91 Brno, Czech Republic

⁴ CEITEC – Central European Institute of Technology, Masaryk University Brno, Kamenice 5, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic

⁵ National Centre for Biomolecular Research, Faculty of Science, Kamenice 5, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic

* To whom correspondence should be addressed.

ChannelsDB 2.0 has been revamped as an upgraded database that offers a comprehensive insight into the structural characteristics, geometry, and physicochemical attributes of protein channels. These channels are drawn from deposited biomacromolecular structures originating from the PDB and AlphaFoldDB databases. In the new version of the ChannelsDB database, the recent data influx has been sourced from various outlets. Primarily, we have incorporated data generated through the widely used CAVER tool, augmenting the insights previously acquired only through the original MOLE tool, which is employed for the detection and analysis of protein tunnels and pores. Additionally, we have extended the database's coverage by introducing tunnels originating from cofactors localised within the AlphaFill database or from cognate ligands within PDB structures. This expansion has increased the available channel annotations by almost five times. ChannelsDB 2.0 houses information concerning geometric properties such as length and radius, as well as physicochemical attributes based on the amino acids lining the channels. These stored data are intricately linked with the existing UniProt mutation annotation data, facilitating in-depth investigations into the functional roles of biomacromolecular tunnels and pores. In summary, ChannelsDB 2.0 represents an invaluable resource for conducting in-depth analyses of the significance of biomacromolecular channels. The database is freely accessible to the public at the address <https://channelsdb2.biodata.ceitec.cz>.

Data Mining and Analysis of Permeability Data from Chemoinformatics Databases

Storchmannová K¹, Balouch M^{2,3} Juračka J^{1,4}, Štěpánek F², Berka K¹

¹ Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University, Olomouc, Czech Republic

² Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Technická 3, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

³ Zentiva k.s., U Kabelovny 130, 102 00 Prague 10, Czech Republic

⁴ Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, 17. listopadu 12, 771 46 Olomouc, Czech Republic

Passive permeability is one of the critical molecular properties that are studied in the first phase of drug discovery because of its strong influence on pharmacokinetics. The quantitative measure of permeability is the permeability coefficient (cm/s), commonly used in its logarithm (LogPerm). Because of the importance of permeability coefficients in pharmaceutical research, numerous experimental and theoretical methods for their determination have been developed. Currently, permeability data is available in literature, but more available in cheminformatics databases e.g. widely known ChEMBL [1], PubChem [2] or MolMeDB [3]. MolMeDB (Molecules on Membranes Database) is a comprehensive and interactive database focused on interactions of molecules with membranes developed at Palacký University Olomouc. Here, we present our low-code data mining approach and analysis in which we have compared and interpreted methods for the determination of permeability based on data available in ChEMBL, PubChem, and MolMeDB. We focused on four experimental and calculated permeability methods.

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Protein dynamics - an overlooked thermodynamic factor

Šulc Josef¹

¹IOCB

This study investigated the impact of connecting different domains in different contexts to a central binding protein. One of the goals was to determine how these modifications affect the ability of the protein to bind small peptide ligands. Specifically, we focused on the PDZ3 domain connected to TrpCage miniproteins at the N-terminus and C-terminus, using glycine linkers of various lengths.

To investigate this phenomenon, we used a combination of molecular dynamics simulations, enhanced sampling techniques, semi-empirical quantum mechanics, and statistical analysis techniques. We analyzed the molecular dynamics of the PDZ3 domain and its connections to the TrpCage miniproteins in different contexts and quantified the resulting changes in dynamical, conformational, and electrostatic behavior. In doing so, we have developed a novel methodology for analyzing the dynamic behavior of multi-domain proteins.

Our analysis revealed that modifying the central binding protein significantly altered its dynamic and conformational behavior, which in turn affected its ability to bind ligands. Specifically, we found that connecting the PDZ3 domain to the TrpCage miniproteins at different termini results in distinct changes in entropy leading to a significant impact on ligand binding. We also observed that one of the protein variants displays IDP-like behaviour.

Our study highlights the importance of considering the dynamic behavior of multi-domain proteins in the design of new proteins and therapeutic macromolecules. By providing a deeper understanding of the relationship between protein dynamics and function, our findings open up new avenues for designing and optimizing protein-protein interactions, with potential applications in drug development and other biotechnological areas. The novel methodology we developed for analyzing protein dynamics, conformations, and electrostatics could be widely applicable to studying other multi-domain proteins as well.

Developing an analytical framework for analyzing the 3D structure and temporal dynamics of dendritic spines

Iva Švecová^{1,2}, Štěpán Kortus²

¹ Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

² Microscopy Service Centre, Institute of Experimental Medicine, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

Dendritic spines are neuronal protrusions that house the postsynaptic component of synaptic connections. Their morphology and dynamics play a crucial role in synaptic plasticity, and alterations in spine density and structure have been implicated in various neurological and neurodegenerative conditions¹. Many traditional studies have relied on fixed-cell light microscopy, often lacking the spatial resolution and temporal information necessary to capture the intricate 3D structure and dynamic behavior of dendritic spines². Recent advancements in live-cell super-resolution microscopy have made it possible to visualize dendritic spines in unprecedented detail, enabling the study of their structural changes over time and their correlation with molecular dynamics, such as receptor surface mobility.

Despite these technological advancements, existing analytical methodologies^{3,4} are typically designed for specific tasks, but lack a unified approach that would integrate both the structural and temporal aspect of dendritic spines. In this project, we aim to leverage existing methods while developing new tools to establish a complete and efficient analytical framework.

As a first step, we have identified several key objectives. These include the high-fidelity 3D reconstruction of dendritic spines from fluorescence microscopy data, accurate separation of individual spines from the dendritic shaft, and the development of a robust method to track the same dendritic spine across multiple time points and objectively analyze structural changes.

The next step will be the integration of spine morphology data with receptor tracking information. This requires addressing the challenge of asynchronous data acquisition, where structural snapshots are obtained at discrete time points while receptor movements occur on different timescales. We will develop an approach to align these datasets temporally, enabling correlation between spine dynamics and receptor mobility.

By creating a robust, multimodal analysis pipeline, this project will provide researchers with an advanced toolset for quantifying dendritic spine structure and function. This framework is expected to contribute to a deeper understanding of synaptic plasticity and its implications in neurological disorders.

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Analysis and Sampling of Molecular Simulations by adversarial Autoencoders

Guglielmo Tedeschi¹, Aleš Křenek², Vojtech Spiwok¹

¹Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology - University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague.

²Institute of Computer Science - Masaryk University, Brno

Molecular dynamics is a computational technique that describes how a given molecular system evolves over time. It facilitates the exploration of stability, conformational changes, and a wide range of other properties. However, the application of molecular dynamics is limited by its high computational cost. The calculations require time steps on the order of femtoseconds to ensure numerical stability and accurately describe molecular motions, which typically occur on a timescale ranging from milliseconds to seconds. Among the various techniques used to enhance simulations, metadynamics operated by encouraging the system to cross high free-energy barriers and explore configurations that would otherwise be inaccessible or difficult to sample. However, for metadynamics to be successful, the collective variables must be carefully designed, relying on both knowledge of the system and user expertise.

Here, we present an Adversarial Autoencoder as an unsupervised approach aimed at designing optimal collective variables. By encoding high-dimensional nonlinear data, collected from unbiased molecular dynamics simulations, into a low-dimensional latent space, the model demonstrates its capability and efficiency in meaningfully interpreting the distribution of the training data. Furthermore, by considering the latent space as a representation of the most relevant features of the system, the model derives optimal collective variable combinations, which are subsequently used to enhance molecular dynamics through metadynamics, resulting in the observation of multiple folding events on significantly reduced timescales.

Moreover, the probabilistic encoding, a distinctive feature that differentiates the employed network from a standard autoencoder, enables the decoding of newly generated structures not present in the training set, thereby enhancing phase-space exploration.

The developed Adversarial Autoencoder demonstrates proficiency in analyzing molecular dynamics simulation data by examining the latent space distribution on classical benchmark proteins commonly used for method development in bioinformatics, such as Alanine Dipeptide, Trp-Cage, and Villin-Headpiece. By extracting the designed collective variables, folding events were observed in Trp-Cage through metadynamics, confirming the effectiveness of the design in optimizing free-energy landscape exploration.

LORA: Lipid Over-Representation Analysis Based on Structural Information

Michaela Vondráčková¹, Dominik Kopczynski², Nils Hoffmann³, Ondřej Kuda¹

¹ Institute of Physiology, Czech Academy of Sciences, Videnska 1083, 14220 Prague, Czechia

² Institute of Analytical Chemistry, University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria

³ Forschungszentrum Jülich, Institute of Bio- and Geosciences (IBG-5), 52428 Jülich, Germany

With the increasing number of lipidomic studies, there is a need for efficient and automated analysis of lipidomic data. One of the challenges faced by most existing approaches to lipidomic data analysis is lipid nomenclature. The systematic nomenclature of lipids contains all available information about the molecule, including its hierarchical representation, which can be used for statistical evaluation. The Lipid Over-Representation Analysis (LORA) web application (<https://lora.metabolomics.fgu.cas.cz>) analyzes this information using the Java-based Goslin framework, which translates lipid names into a standardized nomenclature. Goslin provides the level of lipid hierarchy, including information on headgroups, acyl chains, and their modifications, up to the 'complete structure' level. LORA allows the user to upload experimental query and universe datasets, select a grammar for lipid name normalization, and then process the data. The user can then interactively explore the results and perform lipid overrepresentation analysis based on selected criteria. The results are graphically visualized according to the lipidome hierarchy. The lipids present in the most over-represented terms (lipids with the highest number of enriched shared structural features) are defined as Very Important Lipids (VILs). For example, the main result of a demo dataset is the information that the query is significantly enriched with 'glycerophospholipids' containing 'acyl 20:4' at 'sn-2 position'. These terms define a set of VILs (e.g., PC 18:2/20:4;O and PE 16:0/20:4(5,8,10,14);OH). All results, graphs, and visualizations are summarized in a report. LORA is a tool focused on the smart mining of epilipidomics datasets to facilitate their interpretation at the molecular level.

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Decoding Spatiotemporal Glial Responses in Acute Stroke and Progressive MS Through Scalable Re-Analysis of Spatial Transcriptomics

D. Zucha^{1,2}, A. Nicaise³, S. Pluchino³, L. Valihrach¹

¹ Laboratory of Glial Biology and Omics Technologies, Institute of Biotechnology CAS, Vestec, Czech Republic

² Department of Informatics and Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic

³ Department of Clinical Neurosciences and NIHR Biomedical Research Centre, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom

Abstract. Spatial transcriptomics (ST) has revolutionized neuroimmunology by mapping molecular programs in situ, yet integrating datasets across diseases, species, and scales remains a critical challenge. To address this, we aggregated and re-analyzed 228 ST sections spanning acute ischemic stroke (mouse: 3 studies, 12 sections, days 1–21 post-injury) and progressive multiple sclerosis (PMS; human: 3 studies, 217 sections from 54 patients, white/grey matter lesions). For stroke, murine datasets (n=12, temporal focus on day 3) underwent module scoring and ligand-receptor analysis, revealing early chemokine gradients (Ccl3, Ccl4, Ccl12) in reactive microglia at the infarct border. Strikingly, 100-fold enriched co-expression of ApoE-Trem2 in peri-infarct microglia highlighted spatially resolved lipid-metabolic crosstalk, implicating this axis in glial scar maturation. In PMS, human ST (n=217) leveraged voting-classifier frameworks to identify rare glial populations with SenMayo-linked senescence signatures, spatially correlated with areas of oligodendrocytes loss and demyelination severity, albeit variable between patients. Cross-study patient integration, supported by rigorous technical validation, revealed conserved neuroinflammatory pathways (ApoE-Trem2) and disease-specific glial programs: chemokine-driven scarring in stroke versus senescence-polarized niches in MS. By harmonizing diverse datasets, spanning murine spatiotemporal resolution and human spatial breadth (54 patients) — we established robust pipelines for cross-study ST analysis. These frameworks not only resolve glial heterogeneity but also provide a foundation for collaborative scaling, enabling future studies to incorporate larger cohorts or additional neuroinflammatory conditions. Our work underscores the translational potential of spatially resolved glial signatures, offering mechanistic insights into scar dynamics and senescence.